

SCRUM SPRINT SIMULATION MANUAL

Version 1.2 – April 2026

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document describes a free, lightweight, scalable, and customizable Scrum Sprint simulation designed for classroom use. The activity embodies the execution of a Scrum sprint without coding and in virtual time, which allows it to be completed within a single teaching session.

Compared to traditional project-based approaches to teaching Scrum, the simulation offers the following advantages:

- **Time efficiency** – The activity can be completed in a matter of hours rather than over multiple weeks
- **Focused cognitive load** – By removing the need to produce technical artifacts, e.g., code or tests, the simulation directs learners to concentrate on Scrum roles, events, and decision-making processes
- **Rich scenario coverage** – The simulation incorporates situations that are unlikely to emerge in small-scale academic projects, such as evolving requirements, shifting priorities, refactoring needs, and prolonged absences of team members
- **Collective learning** – The structure of the activity encourages the emergence of differing perspectives within and across teams, creating opportunities for discussion and reflection
- **Timely, situated feedback** – Instructor visibility into team decisions enables real-time intervention, clarification, and exploration of alternative courses of action
- **Sustained engagement** – Game-based elements (e.g., randomness, competition, and physical interaction) support active participation and attention

The simulation is intended for use after learners have been introduced to core Scrum concepts, including roles, events, and artifacts. It is designed to support the transition from conceptual understanding to applied practice by placing learners in a dynamic, event-driven environment.

The activity is characterized by the following properties:

- **Free** – It is available under a Creative Commons license
- **Lightweight** – Uses standard classroom resources (e.g., sticky notes, large-format paper, and a display) and can be set up with minimal preparation time
- **Scalable** – The simulation can be conducted with between 3 and 8 groups without a corresponding increase in the time of the activity
- **Customizable** – The instructor controls which events to include, the rate of progress of the simulated work, and the feedback given

During the simulation, learners:

- · Update a task board, sprint, and release burndown charts with current project status.
- · Make decisions about task selection and allocation.
- · Compute effectiveness and efficiency metrics.
- · Log events and decisions for later reflection.

The simulation runs in about two hours, with an additional hour recommended for setup and reflection. The rest of the manual is organized as follows:

Section 2 – Simulation Engine: Describes the mechanisms that drive the activity,

Section 3 – Workflow and Scripts: Explains how the activity is conducted and the duties of instructors and learners

Section 4 – Parameters: Details the choice of simulation parameters and how they can be changed,

2. SIMULATION ENGINE

The simulation engine encompasses all artifacts used in the simulation activity. It consists of:

- Two lotteries or fortune wheels called the Events Wheel (Figure 1) and the Progress Wheel (Figure 2) which drive the simulation
- The Sprint Backlog which comprises the user stories, technical stories and tasks which are the simulated work elements to be completed in the course of the simulation
- A task board, used to track the status of all work items in the Sprint Backlog
- A release burndown chart used to track the amount of functionality remaining to be completed at the project level, measured in story points
- A sprint burndown chart used to track the amount of work remaining to be completed in the sprint, measured in hours
- A session log to record significant conditions and decisions made

2.1. Events Wheel

Figure 1 Events Wheel. The events can be easily changed via the associated form

The entries in the Events Wheel correspond to unplanned situations that arise in the life of a project such as “A critical defect is reported”, “A new 10-points user story is requested” or “A team member must be absent for 3 days”. As events are drawn, they must be addressed by each of the teams during their daily meetings. Instructors could easily delete existing events or introduce new ones to serve their teaching goals by modifying entries in the associated wheel forms.

Both fortune wheels run on top of Wheel Decide, a web based free online spinner tool that could be found at <https://wheeldecide.com/> (Good as of 3/25/2026) but could be easily implemented through other software. The author has no affiliation with said website, except for being a user. The instantiated URL for the Events Wheel is:

<https://wheeldecide.com/?c1=None&c2=Request%20for%20a%20new%208-points%20user%20story&c3=8-points%20user%20story%20is%20no%20longer%20needed&c4=User%20story%20in%20sprint%20backlog%20is%20deprecated&c5=Team%20member%20%232%20absent%20for%201%20day&c6=Team%20member%20%233%20absent%20for%203%20days&c7=External%20dependency%20discovered&c8=Internal%20dependency%20discovered&c9=High%20priority%20defect%20is%20reported&c10=None&c11=Team%20must%20attend%20full%20day%20meeting&c12=20%20hours%20refactoring%20task%20needed%20&c13=Last%20completed%20user%20story%20is%20rejected&c14=4-hours%20unplanned%20system%20outage&c15=A%20risk%20is%20identified&c16=Expedite%20a%205-points%20user%20story&c17=Team%20member%20%231%20is%20replaced&c18=Low%20priority%20defect%20is%20reported&col=light&t=Events%20Wheel&time=10&width=800>

2.2. Progress Wheel

Figure 2 Progress Wheel

The entries in the Progress Wheel denote individual daily progress hours. Each draw of the wheel will dictate the amount of planned work a team member was able to complete on a given day. For example, if a team assumes 6 hours of effective individual work each day, greater than 6 hours imply the team member achieved more than was planned, i.e. the work was easier than anticipated, entries lower than 6 hours per day denote work that was harder than expected, i.e. lower rate of progress. Our current wheel is calibrated to an expected 5.4 hours of progress with a standard deviation of 2.9 hours, which assures most teams won't be able to complete all planned work and will have to reprioritize some of it. As in the case of the Events Wheel, the mean value and the dispersion of the progress distribution can be changed by changing the value and/or the frequency of the entries in the wheel. Anecdotally, we have observed that extreme entries, e.g. 0 and 12 hours of progress and letting the wheel spin for a moment with a clattering sound helps build anticipation, keeping participants engaged.

The instantiated URL for the Progress Wheel is:

<https://wheeldecide.com/?c1=10%20hrs&c2=1%20hr&c3=4%20hrs&c4=6%20hrs&c5=12%20hrs&c6=5%20hrs&c7=6%20hrs&c8=7%20hrs&c9=5%20hrs&c10=6%20hrs&c11=4%20hrs&c12=7%20hrs&c13=0%20hrs&c14=4%20hrs&c15=8%20hrs&c16=5%20hrs&c17=2%20hrs&c18=5%20hrs&col=light&t=Progres%20Wheel&time=10&width=800>

2.3. Sprint Backlog

User story # 4 User value: 1 Story points: 2	User story # 5 User value: 3 Story points: 5	Technical story # 6 – Database refactoring User value: N/A Effort: 8 hrs.
Task 4.1 Design Effort: 2 hrs.	Task 5.1 Design Effort: 4 hrs.	
Task 4.2 Front-End C&UT Effort: 4 hrs.	Task 5.2 Security Review (This can only be done by team member # 4) Effort: 2 hrs.	
User story # 1 User value: 3 Story points: 3	User story # 2 User value: 3 Story points: 5	User story # 3 User value: 2 Story points: 3
Task 1.1 Design Effort: 4 hrs.	Task 2.1 Design (This task can be started only after TS # 6 has been completed) Effort: 4 hrs.	Task 3.1 Design (This task can be started only after TS # 6 has been completed) Effort: 4 hrs.
Task 1.2 Front-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.	Task 2.2 Security Review (This can only be done by team member # 4) Effort: 2 hrs.	Task 3.2 Front-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.
Task 1.3 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.	Task 2.3 Front-End C&UT Effort: 12 hrs.	Task 3.3 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.
Task 1.4 Acceptance Testing Effort: 4 hrs.	Task 2.4 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.	Task 3.4 Acceptance Testing Effort: 4 hrs.
Task 1.5 Review Effort: 2 hrs.	Task 2.5 Acceptance Testing Effort: 8 hrs.	Task 3.5 Review Effort: 2 hrs.
Task 1.6 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.	Task 2.6 Review Effort: 2 hrs.	Task 3.6 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.
	Task 2.7 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.	

Figure 3 Sprint Backlog

The Sprint Backlog is the collection of simulated work items to be completed during the simulation. It includes user stories and technical stories and the tasks necessary to realize them.

Associated with each user story we would have its relative effort measured in story points, a user value or priority, dependencies on other user stories and any other information the instructor would like to be considered by the learners in the selection of the items to work on. Likewise, tasks will include the effort required measured in hours, and constraints such as special skills required to execute the task and explicit dependencies on the other tasks.

User stories and tasks are assumed to be carried out in a logical fashion, respecting their explicit and implicit dependencies, but since they are not wired into the simulation mechanics, the execution order could be relaxed if it serves a teaching purpose. For example, in one of the simulations, a team asked if it would be ok to bypass a user story by creating an unplanned mock of it to save some time and deliver a higher value one by the end of the sprint. Some tasks are designated for exclusive execution by a specialist, while others to be carried out by anybody. The purpose of this is to force teams to think about the sequencing of work and to create bottlenecks. Again, as

this is not wired into the simulation, it is up to the instructor to control which and how many, if any, different types of tasks to use.

The work items included in the Sprint Backlog could be pre-printed by the instructor on self-adhesive labels or prepared by the learners prior to the simulation, e.g., during a Sprint planning exercise. In the first case, the work across teams is standardized, which facilitates the introduction of dependencies and constraints by the instructor as well as the explanations and comparison of the decisions made by the learners. The second approach might give the learners the opportunity to see the impact of the way their partition of the work has in its execution.

2.4. Task board, burndown charts and session log

Figure 4 Populated task board at the beginning of the Sprint. As the simulation progresses tasks will move from To Do to In Progress, To Done. If an impediment arises the task will be moved to the Blocked column until the issue is resolved. User and technical stories are moved from To Do to Done, when all their subordinated tasks are completed.

Figure 5 Sprint burndown chart. The initial number of hours left will correspond to the sum of the effort of the items in the sprint backlog

Figure 6 Release burndown chart. Assume the total number of story points in the product backlog was 80, during the first sprint you completed 20 story point and during the second 5. Your team is starting Sprint 3 now.

Day	Condition	Decisions / Consequences
2	Team member absent 3 days	Decide to reallocate tasks
4	Team is falling behind schedule	Team goes into overtime
7	Team finishes doing overtime	

Figure 7 Session log. The teams use it to record events and decisions which will inform the reflection session.

The task board, the sprint and the release burndown chart retain their customary Scrum definition and functionality. The log is just a diary for recording consequential decisions for consultation during the reflection session.

3. WORKFLOW AND SIMULATION SCRIPTS

This section describes the materials and rules necessary to simulate the execution of a Scrum Sprint. The recommended simulated time is 10 days, which can be organized as a two-week Sprint or as two one-week sprints to demonstrate the transfer of incomplete or not accepted work from one sprint to the next. Shorter Sprints are not recommended, as it is unlikely learners will be exposed to the full range of situations captured in the simulation.

A simulation session, with a two-week sprint and three to eight participating teams of four to six members each can be run in approximately one and a half to two hours, plus one hour for setup and reflection. A two-sprint simulation session will require an additional half an hour to deal with the handover from one sprint to the next.

Learners are assumed to have an understanding of Scrum and empirical process control prior to the start of the simulation. Figure 8 shows the arrangement of groups in a typical classroom.

Figure 8 Left, front of the class showing the Events and Progress wheels. Right, groups with their material s posted on the walls

Each team will set-up a “station” on a section of the wall, consisting of the task board, the release and the sprint burndown chart canvas and the session log, see Figure 2. The task board will be populated with the user stories and tasks, and here comes the first challenge, drawing the ideal lines for the release and sprint burndown charts. Should the first include technical stories? Should the second include the time spent in daily meetings, backlog refinement and other ceremonies? What are the values of the ordinate at the origin? Since there are no authoritative answers to these questions, rather than arguing who is right and wrong, we prefer to ask what the consequences of the different choices are. This question invites deeper thinking and allows for the presentation and critique of multiple points of view.

Each team then selects a Scrum Master and assigns a consecutive identification number from one up to the number of people in the team to each member; it is advisable to write this number on a self-adhesive name tag to avoid confusion during the simulation. See Figure 9. As will be explained later, this number will associate each team member with their respective Progress Wheel draws. An interesting and easy variation of the simulation is to create two types of teams, one composed of generalists who can perform a variety of tasks and another of

specialists with specific roles, such as front-end developers, back-end developers, and testers and discuss the possible resource contention induced by the specialist organization. Before embarking in the full simulation, is advisable to run one or two practice draws to clarify the mechanics of the exercise.

Figure 9 All participants with the same identification number, irrespective of the team to which they belong, are affected by the same wheel draw

3.1. Simulation Workflow

The simulation workflow for a 10-day sprint is depicted in Figure 10. The simulation starts with each team holding a Scrum meeting (3) to decide which tasks to tackle, dropping ongoing work, who should tackle them, and whether to use overtime or not. Then the instructor spins the Progress Wheel, once for each team member (5), who use the amount of progress drawn, modified by overtime if applicable, to update the remaining effort on the tasks they are working on (6). Note that the draw applies to all team members with the same identification number across all teams. This is the mechanism that allows the simulation to scale.

The Scrum master updates the burndown chart (7). From the second day on, the instructor spins the Events Wheel (1) to draw an event which applies to all teams and must be addressed during the daily scrum meeting (3). Every other simulated day, or in response to the draw of a new event, the instructor asks the teams nudging questions. If

Figure 10 Simulation workflow for a two-weeks sprint

he/she observes something that could be considered a teachable moment, it will pause the simulation to discuss it (2 and 4). To foster engagement, one can give a prize to the team which delivers the most user value at a minimum cost by the end of the sprint.

The use of overtime to accelerate progress is another teachable moment. If a team decides to use overtime, the output from the progress wheel as it applies to each individual member will be multiplied by a factor to give the actual progress. Overtime hours are not as productive as normal hours, not only because as fatigue settles in, we do less, but also because we are likely to introduce more errors which will need to be fixed later at a higher cost later. Also, overtime is usually more expensive as it is paid at a higher rate. This combination of factors is weighed in a team efficiency metric which measures the amount of planned work achieved by every hour of labor put into the Sprint, see Figure 11. Once more, this is not wired in into the simulation, and it is the instructor’s choice whether to use it or not, and what weights to use to reflect the above dynamic.

Amount of overtime decided by the team (Hours)	Coefficient for actual progress
1	1.12
2	1.25
3	1.36
4	1.45

Figure 11 If a team decides to perform two hours of overtime, assuming a Progress Wheel draw of six hours, the actual progress would be $1.25 \times 6 = 7.5$ hours instead of the theoretical $6 + 2 = 8$ hours

After the simulation part of the exercise is concluded we ask learners to reflect on it. We do this at the class and the team levels. The class-wide reflection involves all students present in the class and focuses on discussing the outcomes achieved by their respective teams—such as value delivered and costs incurred—along with the decisions made and the reasoning behind them. Additionally, we ask students about what they have learned and any “aha” moments they might have experienced, we also explore counterfactual scenarios by considering alternative actions and how these might have led to different outcomes. If teams used different team compositions, e.g., specialists versus generalists, we discuss its implications in terms of resource contention, idle times and bottlenecks.

3.2. Detailed simulation script

- 1) Each team member adopts a sequential identification number within its team starting with one, writes it into a self-adhesive nametag and attaches it to his clothes for others to see. One of the members is designated Scrum Master by the team as shown in Figure 9.
- 2) Only active team members participate in the activities below. Team members with absent status as dictated by the Events Wheel cannot take on tasks or contribute to their progress until their absent status expires
- 3) For each day in the sprint
 - a. The instructor spins the Events Wheel. The outcome of the draw applies to all teams
 - b. If the outcome of the draw blocks or somehow prevents the whole team from working, the team loses (skips) the day, and a new cycle is initiated

Figure 12 What will you do today? There is more to this question than meets the eye. See subsection 4.3 for an explanation of the strategies and tactics

- c. Each team holds its own daily stand-up meeting to discuss the Sprint status and how to respond to the Events Wheel draw.
- d. Team members decide what tasks to tackle next, who should work on what and whether to work extra hours or not. See Figure 12. In making these decisions, the teams must consider the impact on productivity and learning of different choices. For example, if the team decides to “specialize” its members by assigning them to areas of work, e.g. “front end” and “back end”, there would be gains in productivity due to the deeper expertise, but this will come at the expense of knowledge sharing and team fungibility. Similarly, assigning an extra person to a task already started to expedite its completion will incur a productivity drop as the new person must become familiar with the work already done at the expense of the person already working on it. In selecting what and who, teams must consider tasks dependencies, tasks that require a unique knowledge and the amount of time left in the Sprint to avoid starting things that cannot be finished.
- e. After all teams have concluded their Daily meeting, the instructor will spin the Progress Wheel as many times as there are members in the largest team. Before each draw, the instructor will announce the identification number of all team members to whom it would apply, remember that the same draw applies to all team members with the same identification number across all teams, each team member then, takes note of the progress that corresponds to him or her, and waits until all draws have been called out
- f. The draw of the Progress Wheel dictates how much progress a team member accomplished in a particular day. If the team is working overtime, the value of the draw should be multiplied by the overtime coefficient defined in the next section
- g. Each team member will choose how to allocate his or her progress to the task or tasks he or she has been assigned. The team members update the number of hours left in the task by subtracting the progress from the previous number of hours left and recording it on the sticky note corresponding to said task. This is very important because it is easy to loose track of the work done. See Figure 13.
- h. Team members, having a significant number of hours left after allocating the corresponding progress to the tasks they were working on, can pull a new task from the Sprint backlog

- i. Tracking. At the end of the simulated day, the Scrum Master looks at what happened during the day and adjusts the Release and the Sprint burndown charts. It is good practice to keep a log of significant decisions such as going into overtime or extraordinary events such as a team member being absent for a couple of days to use in the reflection meeting
- 4) Closing. After the Sprint is over, the team calculates the team's *Velocity*, *Team Efficiency* and the *PercentComplete* metrics. See Figure 14.

Figure 13 Updating the work remaining in a task $WorkRemaining_i = WorkRemaining_{i-1} - ProgressDraw_i$

- 5) The team briefly reflects on things learned in the class, e.g. insights, clarifications, topics for further discussion, things you imagined were a certain way and now you realize are different
- 6) Each Scrum Master presents the results of his or her team to the rest of the class with one or two reflections

Velocity

Velocity is a key metric in Scrum. It has many uses, e.g.: determining how much work the team can tackle in a sprint

$$Velocity = \sum_{Work\ Completed} Story\ Points$$

Team Efficiency

The team efficiency metric measures the amount of planned work achieved by every hour of labor put into the Sprint.

$$TeamEfficiency = \frac{\sum_{All\ tasks\ completed} Planned\ hours}{Regular\ Development\ hours - Hours\ due\ to\ absences + 1.5 \times Overtime\ hours}$$

Percentage Completed

The percentage completed metric measures the amount of completed work in relation to the amount of committed work.

$$PercentageCompleted = \frac{\sum_{Work\ Completed} Story\ Points}{\sum_{Work\ Committed} Story\ Points}$$

Figure 14 Team metrics

4. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

This section describes miscellaneous information about the meaning of the data used in the simulation and how the author uses it. As mentioned before, these are not wired into the simulation, and instructors can change them to better fit their learning objectives.

4.1. Events Wheel

The Events Wheel depicts common situations arising in the life of any Scrum project that must be addressed by the team while performing its planned Sprint work.

As there are more events of interest than days on the Sprint, not every one of them would be covered during its execution. For this reason, whenever sensible, events have been grouped in pairs, see shaded elements on Table 1, such as when one is draw, after discussing it with the teams, the instructor could ask the group how to deal with the other and why.

Table 1 Events' definition

Event	Ask complementary event	Explanation	Lesson
None		Nothing special happens that day	The team goes about doing its work
Request for a new 8-points user story	Y	The PO request a new user story that is not in the backlog	User story is incorporated to the Product Backlog for further discussion. No impact on the ongoing sprint
Expedite a 5-points user story	Y	The PO request the incorporation of an unscheduled user story to the current sprint	Work in the current sprint should not be disturbed. If it is a new user story, it should be incorporated to the product backlog
8-points user story is no longer needed	Y	The PO informs the team that a user story sitting in the PB is no longer needed	Update product backlog
User story in sprint backlog is deprecated	Y	The PO informs the team that a user story the team is currently working on is no longer needed	Update product and sprint backlog
Team member #2 absent for 1 day	Y	A team member will be absent for one day	Is it worth reallocating pending work?

Event	Ask complementary event	Explanation	Lesson
Team member #3 absent for 3 days	Y	A team member will be absent for three days	This could delay work carried out by other team members, so it is prudent to study implications
Team member #1 replaced by a new hire		A team member leaves the project and is replaced by a new hire	How do you address learning in the middle of a project?
External dependency discovered	Y	A dependency the team cannot resolve by itself is identified during the execution of a task	Coordination with external team, reprioritization
Internal dependency discovered	Y	A dependency the team can resolve is identified during the execution of a task	Reprioritization, blocking, unplanned work
High priority defect is reported	Y	A defect that causes the system to become completely inoperable or inaccessible to a large number of users and for which there is no work around available	Work must be stopped, and people reallocated to solve it
Low priority defect is reported	Y	A defect whose solution could be postponed	The product backlog must be updated
Team must attend a full day meeting			No work in planned items
20 hours refactoring task needed		During the execution of a task the need to refactor the code before proceeding is identified	Unplanned work, blocking
Last completed user story is rejected		The PO gave the OK to a user story, but this is later rejected by the users	Update product backlog
4-hours unplanned system outage		A four-hour systems outage prevents the team from working on their computers	No work in planned items
A new risk is identified		While implementing a user story, the team identifies a new risk	Update product backlog to deal with it

4.2. Progress Wheel

The Progress Wheel shows the amount of planned work a team member was able to complete in a single day of work. The standard rate of progress per day is set at six hours per day. Six hours is used instead of the nominal eight work hours, since around 20% of the worktime is spent on Scrum ceremonies, personal conversations, etc. To simulate tasks that are easier or more complicated than what was estimated, the simulation uses amounts of progress above or below the standard six hours. For example, a wheel entry of eight hours denotes a progress that is 33% above the standard and an entry of twelve hours double the progress, meaning the task was way easier than anticipated. Similarly, a wheel entry of three hours means that the portion of the task executed that day was twice as hard as anticipated.

The distribution of progress values goes from zero to twelve hours of progress per day per team member. See Table 6. To mimic the normal underestimation of work efforts, the distribution has a main value of 5.33 with a slight skew to the right.

More drastic effects can be achieved by changing this distribution.

Table 2 Progress Wheel entries

Hours
10
1
4
6
12
5
6
7
5
6
4
7
0
4
8
5
2
5

Mean	5.38
Median	5
Mode	5
Standard Deviation	2.91
Minimum	0
Maximum	12

4.3. Explanation of the strategies and tactics in Figure 12

These definitions are not wired in into the simulation and do not pretend to be a complete set. The instructor might choose a different set.

Table 3 How will work be allocated? Representative strategies.

Ways of Working	Description	Primary intent	Key trade-offs
Task pulling	Default Scrum policy. Whoever is available takes the next selected Sprint Backlog task	Minimum resource contention. Minimum coordination requirements	Requires dash (generalists) or T or π (generalists with one or two areas of expertise) shaped skills profiles
Story pulling	Team members (individually or collaboratively) focus on completing a single backlog item end-to-end, taking responsibility for all associated tasks until the item is done	Minimize handoffs	Requires dash (generalists) or T or π (generalists with one or two areas of expertise) shaped skills profiles. Might artificially induce task serialization
Specialist team	Team members work on the next selected Sprint Backlog task within defined competencies	Maximize efficiency	If work requirements and team skills are not balanced it will induce team contention. There might be single points of failure
Work-sharing	Tasks are primarily handled by specialists, but team members collaborate or take on work outside their expertise when needed to balance workload, reduce bottlenecks, or support delivery goals	Exploit the benefits of specialization while mitigating its problems	Bystander effect might result in tasks falling through the cracks. Requires strong clan control
Role rotation	Team members deliberately take work across technical domains or task types to build broader competence	Promote individual development, build team resilience	Temporary inefficiencies due to learning curves of individual team members and team's reconfigurations (storming and norming in Tuckman's model)

Table 4 How do we select the next Sprint Backlog item? Representative rules.

Sprint backlog item selection rule	Inputs	Explanation	Rationale/consequence
Capacity first	People (skills) available, time left in the Sprint	Work that if started today could be completed by the end of the Sprint	Minimize unfinished work at the end of the Sprint
Finish first	Tasks belonging to items closer to completion	Stop starting, Start finishing	Maximize work completed at the end of the Sprint
User value first	Product Owner priorities	Deliver the most value first	Could be more costly if the natural order of work is ignored
High-leverage first	Number of work items depending on this one	Future work enabled by completing this item	Maximize parallel work and future choices
Drop	Capacity shortfall, priority changes	A planned task is removed from the backlog before work begins due to changing priorities or feasibility concerns	Impact on dependencies, incomplete goals

Table 5 How do we allocate resources, how much time do we work and how do we dispose of work items?

Execution tactic	Applies to	Description	Primary intent	Key trade-offs
Ordinary pull	New work item	A single team member is allocated to work on the next selected backlog item	Maintain steady flow with minimal coordination	If team members are specialized this tactic is likely to produce resource contention
Assisting (swarming)	Work item in progress	Team members are brought into an in-progress task to help. The motivation is to solve a problem, not to speed up development.	Unblock a task, finish on-time	The newly assigned team members need time to get up to speed
Crashing (swarming)	New work item	Multiple team members are assigned to the next selected backlog item to reduce its completion time, acknowledging potential coordination overhead	Speed-up work completion	Coordination overhead, diminishing returns
Pairing	New work item	Two team members are assigned to the next selected backlog item	Promote quality, learning, risk reduction	Reduced short-term throughput
Substituting	Work item in progress	A different team member takes over an in-progress task due to the unavailability of the original assignee.	Maintain steady flow	Length of the absence should be balanced against context transfer costs
Multitasking (opportunistic)	Blocked work items	A team member switches between tasks when progress on one is blocked or delayed	Take advantage of idle time during waiting periods	If abused will result in productivity losses due to learning and forgetting effects and longer work item completion times
Multitasking (contention)	Sprint under stress	A team member is allocated to multiple active tasks	Maintain progress across multiple work items	High context switching costs, longer work item completion times
Overtime	Sprint under stress	Team members work beyond normal hours to increase short-term output	Complete more work	If abused results in reduced quality, increased fatigue, diminishing productivity over time and increased turn-over
Preempting	Work item in progress	An in-progress task is interrupted so a team member can be reassigned to higher-priority work	Responsiveness to work changes	Forgetting and relearning effects upon work item resumption. Impact on dependencies
Abandoning	Work item in progress	An in-progress work item is permanently stopped and removed from the sprint scope	Stop a feature that is no longer valuable, abandon a failing approach	Dependency impact. Avoid sunk cost fallacy

5. TEMPLATE SPRINT BACKLOG WORK ITEMS – USE AVERY 55160 EASY PEEL REPOSITIONABLE ADDRESS LABELS

<p>User story # 1 User value: 3 Story points: 3</p>	<p>User story # 2 User value: 3 Story points: 5</p>	<p>User story # 3 User value: 2 Story points: 3</p>
<p>Task 1.1 Design Effort: 4 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 2.1 Design (This task can be started only after TS # 6 has been completed) Effort: 4 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 3.1 Design (This task can be started only after TS # 6 has been completed) Effort: 4 hrs.</p>
<p>Task 1.2 Front-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 2.2 Security Review (This can only be done by team member # 4) Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 3.2 Front-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.</p>
<p>Task 1.3 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 2.3 Front-End C&UT Effort: 12 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 3.3 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.</p>
<p>Task 1.4 Acceptance Testing Effort: 4 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 2.4 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 3.4 Acceptance Testing Effort: 4 hrs.</p>
<p>Task 1.5 Review Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 2.5 Acceptance Testing Effort: 8 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 3.5 Review Effort: 2 hrs.</p>
<p>Task 1.6 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 2.6 Review Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 3.6 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.</p>
	<p>Task 2.7 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	

<p>User story # 4 User value: 1 Story points: 2</p>	<p>User story # 5 User value: 3 Story points: 5</p>	<p>Technical story # 6 – Database refactoring User value: N/A Effort: 8 hrs.</p>
<p>Task 4.1 Design Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 5.1 Design Effort: 4 hrs.</p>	
<p>Task 4.2 Front-End C&UT Effort: 4 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 5.2 Security Review (This can only be done by team member # 4) Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	
<p>Task 4.3 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 5.3 Front-End C&UT Effort: 16 hrs.</p>	
<p>Task 4.4 Acceptance Testing Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 5.4 Back-End C&UT Effort: 8 hrs.</p>	
<p>Task 4.5 Review Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 5.5 Acceptance Testing Effort: 8 hrs.</p>	
<p>Task 4.6 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	<p>Task 5.6 Review Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	
	<p>Task 5.7 Commit Effort: 2 hrs.</p>	